

- *Supplementary material for Crespi Isabella, Lomazzi Vera, "Gender mainstreaming and gender equality in Europe: policies, legislation and Eurobarometer surveys", Studi di Sociologia (2018/1)*

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The file includes supplementary material mentioned in the manuscript " Gender mainstreaming and gender equality in Europe: Policies, legislation and Eurobarometer surveys " submitted to the journal *Studi di Sociologia*. The file reports a summary of the main steps of the EU legislation on gender equality and gender mainstreaming from 1957 to 2017 (Table 1); and an overview of the topics on gender issues investigated by the Eurobarometer by round between 1975 and 2016 (Table 2).

Table 1 Gender equality (and gender mainstreaming) legislation (1957-2017)

Year	Legislative act	Description
1957	Treaty of Rome (Art 119)	The Treaty incorporates the principle of equal pay for equal work for the same job between men and women in each Member State.
1996	European Commission's Communication on Incorporating Equal Opportunities for Women and Men into all Community Policies and Activities	Gender mainstreaming is indicated as a strategy for the promotion of gender equality in all Commission policies and activities, alongside the implementation of specific measures
1997	Treaty of Amsterdam	The Treaty strengthens the legal basis for Community action in favor of gender equality. Arts. 2 and 3 formalize the Community commitment to gender mainstreaming by establishing equality between women and men as a specific task of the Community as well as a horizontal objective affecting all Community policies and programmes.
2000	Council of Europe in Lisbon	The European Union sets out the so-called Lisbon strategy, which include the goal of obtain within ten years new objectives for women in employment: increasing female employment rates up to 60% and until then, European governments had mainly aimed at reducing unemployment rates.
2003	European Parliament resolution on gender mainstreaming in the European Parliament	It expresses the commitment to regularly adopt and implement a policy plan for gender mainstreaming. It suggests guidelines for implementing gender mainstreaming in the committees' and delegations' policy work.
2006	EU Roadmap for Equality between Women and Men for 2006-2010	It outlines priorities such as: equal economic independence for women and men, reconciliation of private and professional life, equal representation in decision-making, eradication of all forms of gender-based violence and elimination of gender stereotypes, promotion of

		gender equality in external and development policies.
2006	First European Pact for Gender Equality	The Pact demonstrates the Member States' determination to implement policies aimed at promoting the employment of women and guaranteeing a better balance between professional and private life in order to meet the challenges of demographic change. The Pact encourages actions in the following fields: measures to close gender gaps and combat gender stereotypes in the labor market, measures to promote a better work-life balance for all and measures to reinforce governance through GM and better monitoring.
2007	TFEU - Treaty on the functioning of the European Union	Art. 19 provides the legal base for combatting discrimination based on sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation. The Treaty applies the principle of gender mainstreaming in many other fields: 'In all its activities, the Union shall aim to eliminate inequalities, and to promote equality between women and men' (Art.8); social exclusion and discrimination (Art.9); principle of equality between man and woman with regard to labor market opportunities and treatment (Art. 157); prevention and action against all kinds of trafficking and sexual abuse of women (Art. 79); the fight against domestic violence (Declaration on Article 8 of TEU).
2008	Communication "Non-discrimination and equal opportunities: A renewed commitment"	This document reinforces the European Union's approach in fighting discrimination on the grounds of race or ethnicity, religion or belief, disability, age, gender or sexual orientation and promoting equal opportunities. It seeks to ensure that everyone is given a fair chance to realize his or her potential and that EU strengthening the fight against discrimination through policy tools for active promotion of equal opportunities.
2009	Treaty of Lisbon	The Treaty includes enhancements to the social dimension of the European Union. It adds the non-discrimination principle and equality between women and men to the values of the European Union (Art. 2 TEU) and mandates that the Union shall combat discrimination and promote equality between women and men (Art. 3 TEU).
2010	Strategy for Equality between Women and Men for 2010-2015	In this Strategy, the Commission has specified gender equality goals for each priority field. Furthermore, all Directorates-General are invited to set gender equality objectives in the Commission's yearly programming cycle and work programme. The Commission's 2010-2015 strategy for equality between women and men prioritized in particular increase of female labor-market participation, reducing gender pay gap, promoting gender equality in decision-making, fighting gender violence and promoting gender equality across the world.
2010	Charter of Fundamental Rights	Art. 21: the principle of non-discrimination based on any ground, including sex. Art. 23: women's rights and gender equality, affirming that 'equality between women and men must be ensured in all areas, including employment, work and pay'.
2011	European Pact for Gender Equality 2011-2020	The Council reaffirms its commitment to fulfil EU ambitions on gender equality and in particular to: - close the gender gaps in employment and social protection, including the gender pay gap, with a view to meeting the objectives of the Europe

		<p>2020 Strategy;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - promote better work-life balance for women and men throughout the life-course; - combat all forms of violence against women in order to ensure the full enjoyment by women of their human rights and to achieve gender equality.
2016	Strategic Engagement for Gender Equality 2016-2019	<p>It continues to corroborate the 2011-2020 European Pact for gender equality through a reference framework for increased effort at all levels, be they European, national, regional or local. Promoting gender equality is still reinforced as a core activity for the EU: equality between women and men is a fundamental EU value, an EU objective and a driver for economic growth.</p>
2016	The H2020 Programme Guidance on Gender Equality in Horizon 2020	<p>This is the most recent document regarding the implementation of Gender equality. Through this guidance, gender is introduced as a key point in the research and in the scientific field. In Horizon 2020, gender is a cross-cutting issue and is mainstreamed in each of the different parts of the Work Programme, ensuring a more integrated approach to research and innovation. The main interesting and innovative aspect is that gender equality entered the field of science and research in a strong way for example by requiring gender balance in research teams and in decision-making bodies but also by integrating the gender dimension in research and innovation (R&I) content.</p>

Table 2: Topics on gender issues investigated by the Eurobarometer by round (1975-2016)

Year	Eurobarometer round	Study number*	Topic of set of variables in EB: label
1975	EB 3	ZA0987	European Men and Women Women's role in society and work. Differences between the sexes
1977	EB 8	ZA0992	Family roles (housewife and work) and Women's role in politics
1979	EB 11	ZA1036	Child care and family planning
1983	EB 19	ZA1318	Women's role in society, work and politics
1987	EB 27	ZA1712	Women's role in society and work and legislation protecting women's rights
1989	EB 32	ZA1752	Family planning: number of children, role of family in society and what government can do to improve families
1993	EB 39.0	ZA2346	Family planning and policy: role of mothers and fathers, as infant care leave, availability of child care
1994	EB 41	ZA2490	Women policy in the EU and Women in decision making bodies
1994	EB 41.1	ZA2491	Women and European Elections (female candidates in EU elections) and Women in decision making bodies
1994	EB 42	ZA2563	Family roles: Family work-family balance about the mother working and childcare
1996	EB 44.3 VOR	ZA2829	Women's unemployment and sex equality: the current work situation for women. impact of women's working on the well-being of men, children, women, families, and couples
1997	EB 47.1	ZA2936	Family planning and work situations and in particular ideal work situation while rearing children
1997	EB 47.2 OVR	ZA2938	Young respondents Working women and family planning and work situations
1998	EB 50.1	ZA3086	Family planning and policy
1999	EB 51.0	ZA3171	Domestic violence against women
2001	EB 56.2	ZA3627	Family planning
2002	EB 57	ZA3638	Discrimination they may have experienced or seen at work, in education, in seeking housing or as a customer of retail or other Discrimination: racial or ethnic origin, gender, religion or beliefs, disability (physical disability, learning difficulties or mental illness) age and sexual orientation.
2003	EB 59.0	ZA3903	Family planning / Partnership, child care and housework
2003	EB 59.1	ZA3904	Parental leave: more specifically about the attitudes of men toward taking time off from the workforce for parental leave. Questions addressed the main reasons that would

			encourage or discourage fathers from taking parental leave.
2004	EB 62.2	ZA4231	A series of questions addressed discrimination experience in general.
2006	EB 65.4	ZA4508	Discrimination The six legally prohibited forms of discrimination in the EU are examined: discrimination on the basis of sex, ethnic origin, religion or beliefs, age, disability and sexual orientation.
2006	EB 65.1	ZA4505	Family planning the roles of men and women in raising children, the ideal ages for men and women to have children, and solutions for potential shortages in the workforce.
2006	EB 65.3	ZA4507	Family planning the roles of men and women in raising children, the ideal ages for men and women to have children, and solutions for potential shortages in the workforce.
2008	EB 69.1	ZA4743	Discrimination Several new questions are also asked in the current survey, for example dealing with the subject of 'multiple discrimination'. In the report the six legally prohibited forms of discrimination in the EU are examined: discrimination on the basis of gender, ethnic origin, religion or beliefs, age, disability and sexual orientation.
2009	Flash 266	ZA4891	Women and European elections: examine women's attitudes and behaviour towards elections in general and their opinions about the European elections and activities of the European Parliament in particular.
2009	EB 71.2	ZA4972	Discrimination: the economic crisis has lowered confidence that governments will promote equality, and increased the belief that discrimination will rise.
2009	EB 72.2	ZA4976	Gender equality This report presents the results of the survey in four main sections; 1 PERCEPTION OF GENDER EQUALITY IN EUROPE The first section seeks to gauge the current situation, perceptions of the evolution of gender equality in the last ten years, knowledge of rights and personal experience of gender-based discrimination, the persistence of stereotypes, and the priorities for action. 2 GENDER EQUALITY IN DIFFERENT DOMAINS The second part focuses on different aspects of life which might have an impact on gender equality. 3 FIGHTING GENDER INEQUALITY – THE ROLE OF THE EU The third section looks at the role of the European Union and an overview of the efforts made to date. 4 GENDER EQUALITY IN THE FUTURE The fourth and final section looks to the future in 2030 and asks Europeans to assess whether gender equality will be more or less prevalent.
2010	EB 73.2	ZA5232	Domestic violence against women: this survey shows a greater awareness of domestic violence and desire for

			tougher action to clamp down on it.
2011	EB 75.1 EP	ZA5479	Women in the EU: This Eurobarometer is part of wave 75.1 and covers the special topic of women in the EU. Questions in this survey pertain to gender equality and work, including gender pay gap and paternal leave. Other questions addressed women's representation in politics and violence against women.
2011	EB 76.1	ZA5565	Gender equality: focuses on gender balance in business leadership and Women in decision-making positions: General associations with gender equality ♦ Equal representation of women and men in positions of responsibility ♦ How to achieve gender balance on company boards ♦ Legislation for more balanced representation of women and men on company boards
2012	EB 77.4	ZA5613	Discrimination in the EU in 2012 Perceptions on discrimination against transsexual and transgender persons are also explored for the first time.
2014	EB 82.4	ZA5933	Gender equality: About how widespread gender inequalities are in their country; on whether they think equality between men and women is a fundamental right; on whether tackling gender inequality should be an EU priority.
2015	EB 83.4	ZA6595	Discrimination: Also for the first the survey is looking into social acceptance and citizens' views on the rights of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender persons.
2016	EB 85.3	ZA6695	Gender-based violence about gender-based violence. Among others, it explores the following topics: • Opinions about and attitudes towards gender-based violence; • Perceptions of the prevalence of domestic violence and sexual harassment; • Personal knowledge of a victim of domestic violence, and to whom people speak in the case of knowledge of domestic violence; • Whether a range of acts of gender-based violence are wrong and are, or should be, illegal.

*Study number refers to the GESIS Data Catalogue (<https://dbk.gesis.org/dbksearch/home.asp>).

Detailed information on the variables can be retrieved also on the ZACAT platform at GESIS, Data Archive Cologne: <http://zocat.gesis.org/webview/>